

Employee Participation and Digital Citizenship Behaviour of Public Universities in Delta State

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Abstract

The paper discusses the concept of Employee participation and Digital citizenship behaviour. It investigates the effect of participatory decision making, using AI technology to enhance educational activities of public universities in Delta State. The statement of the problem is based on the noticeable poor level of ethical digital behaviour by majority of academic staff members. Many are non-tech savvy and nonchalant to learn. Notably, previous studies have observed technical expertise gained for analog operations for delivering course materials and assessments. However, this study seek to bridge the research gap of limited studies relating to the over-reliance on analog systems, impact of high cost in digital training, nonchalant participation in digital practices, curbing unethical and unregulated use of AI. For this purpose, a cross sectional study was conducted with a purposive approach using qualitative data obtained from sixty-six (66) academic staff of three (3) Public Universities in Delta State; namely, Nigeria Maritime University, Southern Delta University, and Dennis Osadebe University. Data collected was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings were also drawn from reviewed literature. The study revealed that public universities still rely on physical human interaction and participation. However, there is a significant relationship between variables of employee participation and digital citizenship behaviour. In conclusion, the employees with teamwork participation etiquette, and digital problem solving tendencies performed better. Therefore, the paper recommends dynamic management polices, to sustain academic integrity, improve employee participation and promote digital citizenship behaviour.

Keywords: Public Universities; Employee Participation; Digital Citizenship Behaviour; Artificial Intelligence

Introduction

Public Universities are government-owned citadels of learning. They serve as centers for employment opportunities for both skilled and non-skilled individuals. They are functional in building the leaders of tomorrow (Akinbo, 2025). They contribute to economic, sociocultural and environmental progress of nations. Also, employees in public universities play crucial roles through participation in educational activities using Artificial Intelligence popularly known as AI (Maikudi et al., 2025). Essentially, Artificial intelligence is a computer programme with the ability to mimic human cognizance for solving real life problems. Apparently, it is still subject to the strong sentiments of the human elements, such as students and lecturers involved. Meanwhile, the concept

of digital citizenship behaviour is also gaining traction. Digital citizenship behaviour is an ideology based on active, inclusive and responsible digital practices. Moreover, organizations are now adopting paperless documentations, and virtual activities (Bano, 2025). Over 71% of workplaces now organize virtual meetings for collective bargaining, and transmit academic materials accessible to a large audience conveniently (Barbu et al., 2025). However, in recent years some scholars have argued that the adoption of AI is a threat to the survival of key academic paradigms, including measurement and evaluation of student and staff performance (Mishra et al., 2025).

Purpose of the study

1. Investigate the relationship between task-based participation and digital citizenship behaviour of selected public universities in Delta State.
2. To examine the relationship between representative participation and digital citizenship behaviour of selected public universities in Delta State.
3. Examine the relationship between pseudo-participation and digital citizenship behaviour of selected public universities in Delta State.

Statement of the problem

Ideally, the rise of Artificial intelligence (AI) has prompted institutions to switch from traditional assessments to digital alternatives for efficiency purposes. In the same vain, there are also AI detectors that ensures authenticity of academic materials, such as Turnitin, Originality.ai, Plagscan etc.

Notably, previous researchers have unraveled the problem of delay and lapses in academic activities. However, the gap in literature is that these past research works have not adequately examined the reality of modern-day work environment. The first problem here is that, the unchecked adoption of AI leads to job displacement, increased demand for tech-savvy employees, costly training and retraining workshops. Furthermore, digital initiatives are costly for public universities with limited funding and low-paid employees. Moreover, well-meaning employees intend to participate but are disadvantaged for they are not paid enough to personally afford and acquire the technical/ethical knowledge. Imperatively, there is the common problem of poor staff welfare in our public universities, which cannot be downplayed by the academic unions to prioritize technological adoption.

So it is crucial to address these issues. Essentially, the study seek to incorporate an extensive literature review and field study coupled with due diligence and wide consultations that would bridge the gaps and mitigate the issues raised.

Figure 1: Framework for the study on Employee Participation and Digital Citizenship Behaviour

Figure 1: Framework for the study on Employee Participation and Digital Citizenship Behaviour Literature Review

Concept of Employee Participation

Employee participation can be referred to an the active work approach. According to the American Federation of Labour, active work is ‘a fair days labour for a fair days pay’. Employee participation implies a positive adoption of new polices, technologies and shared understanding (Abome, 2025). It promotes inclusiveness; It changes the air of negativity, and clash of opinions between top and bottom level employees (Imasuen & Chinwe, 2025). There are various dimensions of employee participation

Dimensions of employee participation

Task-based participation

In this study, the first dimension of employee participation is called task-based participation. This is about a focus on the actual job rather than office politics (Akinbo, 2025). Task-based participation as explained by Imasuen & Chinwe (2025) is a form of employee participation that improves service quality. In this dimension, managers in the human resources department, have a strategic duty to ensure there is employee-job-fit, or workers-task-fit, at the point of recruitment and selection (Barbu et al., 2025). Task-based management practice leads to job satisfaction, for the employee would be doing what he or she does best. However, the negative side of manual task-based participation is task repetition which could lead to depression from repeating a particular role for years to come (Bano, 2025). By so doing while other employees are advancing and growing through the ranks, some are stuck on one level and non-tech savvy. This is where AI task-based participation is recommended. As online and hybrid learning continue to grow in popularity, it is critical that employees University administrative and academic staff inclusive, have a certain level of proficiency with various technologies. In order for them to enhance their administrative duties and teaching service.

Representative Participation

Representative participation as a form of employee participation is self explanatory. A suitable example is trade or labour union representation. Unionism in Nigeria is constitutional. It is the viable avenue to curb the increasingly questionable political and corporate governance (Barbu et al., 2025). Though it is perceived as a confrontational approach to promote employee voice, it can be an avoidable peaceful protest when demands are timely met. In the Nigeria for example, labour strike actions are upheld by various unions for better work conditions and welfare packages. Unions are set to protect members interest including the pursuit of job satisfaction. Essentially, University employees may lose their jobs as a result of integrating AI. Inevitably, tasks such as data entry and computations manually performed by 10 employees can be reduced to 2 highly trained AI prompters. This possibility is a cause for ethical questions about the impact of AI on the academic profession. To ensure AI is used responsibly and fairly in higher education, it is imperative that these ethical issues be addressed during the adoption process. It should be regarded as a relative challenge been faced by the staff members that are represented (Bano, 2025).

Pseudo-participation

This is an approach to management in which managers cultivate an impression of openness but are careful to retain decision-making in their own hands (Abome et al., 2025). Pseudo-participation is the illusion some workers create about themselves. They are passive about work related activities, but have faith that all things will work together for their good and for the good of the organization (Bano, 2025). The downside of this participation is the tendency of low service quality overtime. In reality positive changes that absolutely favors employees' is rare but these set of employees keep the faith at the expense of their job satisfaction (Mishra et al., 2025). This laid-back work attitude also reflects in pseudo adoption of technologies. This form of employee participation is associated with the use of direct communication and other weak forms that are not entirely transparent (Maikudi et al., 2025). Some organisations promise AI capabilities when the system is actually relying on human intervention can be misleading. Some schools promise automated script marking but behind the scene, the opposite is done, with the excuse of breakdown in technological infrastructure (Akinbo, 2025).

Concept of Digital Citizenship Behaviour

According to Shoab et al. (2025) the term Digital Citizenship behaviour is about responsible and active participation in the digital world. Digital citizenship behaviour involves understanding and using digital technologies such as Artificial intelligence responsibly, including showing respect for intellectual property, practicing online safety and engaging in constructive communication. Individuals under the concept are able to access information, share their voices, and participate in shaping the digital world. While digital citizenship offers opportunities. it also presents challenges like the digital divide, misinformation, and potential for misuse of technology.

Measures of Digital Citizenship Behaviour

Digital citizenship behaviour can be measured in different ways or forms. The purpose of digital citizenship behaviour measurement is to help in making decisions and to understand progress towards meeting the deadline for technological adoption (Bano, 2025). Significantly, the researcher has gone further to identify three (3) indicators that are appropriate for the research in-view. They are communication, problem solving and team work.

Communication

According to Maikudi et al. (2025) communication is a vital component for enhancing service quality, but it is perceived as a weak form of employee participation often than not, it implies a

top-down instruction approach. Unless, the organization has a flexible structure where employees can be informed through a two-way dialogue, without hierarchy and authority standing as barrier. In the society today, communication transform individuals and businesses beyond measure especially where technological medium is introduced to speedup dissemination of important messages through emails, written memos, internal newsletters, company intranet, social media platform like Twitter, Facebook and Whatsapp etc (Alabi & Mutula, 2025).

Problem-solving

According to Barbu et al. (2025) problem solving is the ability to identify and resolve issues as they arise. It is evident that this capacity can be demonstrated efficiently through the use of technology. However, the pattern of communication whether flexible or rigid can affect how digital tools such as AI can be adopted for effectively (Abome et al., 2025). This implies that principal officers should consider strategies that allow employees to suggest better ways to handle tasks (Shoab et al., 2025). However, there will be 'too many captains on one boat', if the organization is not careful in allowing opinions and new approach to fly around (Maikudi et al., 2025). Hence, to ensure AI is used responsibly and fairly, it is crucial that institutions properly design and incorporate it.

Teamwork

Teamwork is a form of digital citizenship that also entail self-managed teams. Employees are free to work independently and interdependently (Imasuen & Chinwe, 2025). Team-working is a common topic in the University. Working in teams prepares us for a healthy competition in the labour market (Adesina & Egbuta, 2025). Also, digital citizenship in the category of student and staff teamwork, Institutions have come to many significant realisations as a result of the sudden shift to online and distant learning within the last two years (Barbu et al., 2025).

Theoretical review

Theory selected for the study is the Adam's Equity theory

The study is anchored on the Adams' Equity Theory. Adams argued that employee motivation to voluntarily participate at work is influenced by their perception of fairness in the workplace compared to others (Bano, 2025). Adam stresses the point that 'Everyone should be carried along'. How Management reacts to the contribution of one employee compared to others, can trigger motivation or demotivation. The level of reward and recognition a staff member gets for a job well done, in comparison to others, can trigger motivation or demotivation, job satisfaction or dissatisfaction. Practically, when the use of AI by some workers is demonised, while a few are allowed to use it discreetly, this can disturb the unity in the work environment (Adesina & Egbuta, 2025).

Empirical Review

The study by Alonta et al. (2025) investigated how artificial intelligence (AI) may improve the digital literacy and communication abilities of small business owners in Nigeria. A survey approach was favoured. Using accidental sampling approach, 105 respondents (SME operators) from Anambra State were chosen. A self-administered questionnaire was adopted. The data collected was interpreted using weighted mean analysis. The study concluded that AI is essential for improving SME operators' digital literacy and communication abilities in Anambra State, Nigeria. As a result, it was suggested that SME owners in Nigeria's Anambra State invest in AI-powered training programs to improve their digital marketing skills and use AI-powered tools to improve their communication skills.

Also, the study by Omodu (2025) investigated how artificial intelligence is used in public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria, for staff mentorship and instructional efficiency. The research

design used in the study was correlational. The study's focus was Rivers State's public universities. 1,186 senior teachers from three Rivers State universities. Using random sampling, a sample size of 302 senior academics from the three universities was selected from the population. The respondents were asked to complete two structured questionnaires. The Pearson product moment correlation analysis was employed. According to the findings, academic staff performance of Rivers State universities is positively impacted by the use of AI in staff mentoring as well as student evaluation. The study concluded that senior academic staff at different universities should promote the use of AI, lecturers' cooperation and synergy to increase productivity.

Methods

This study adopted the descriptive research to investigate the relationship between employee participation and digital citizenship behaviour of public universities in Delta state. The population comprises staff of Nigeria Maritime University, Okerenkoko; Southern Delta University, Ozoro and Dennis Osadebe University, Asaba. The sample size of the study is the accessible population (Adamu, 2016). For the sake of convenience, information was obtained from only three (3) notable public universities in Delta State mentioned earlier. The Universities provided us the data of persons on functional departments within the school, they were seventy-five (75) altogether in these three Universities. The sample size was justified as a reliable sample size of 64; according to the Taro Yamane method below:

$$n = \frac{N}{K + N(e)^2}$$

N = Population of study

K = Constant (1)

e = degree of error expected

n = sample size

Therefore;

Population of study: 75

Expected Degree of Error: 0.05

$$n = \frac{75}{1 + 75(1 + 0.0025)}$$
$$\frac{75}{1.1875}$$

$$n = 63.46788525 = 64$$

Stratified sampling technique was employed to ensure that all the categories of the workers in the selected public universities in Delta State, with respect to their designations were represented in the sample for this study. The primary data collection was initiated to retrieve first hand data, which helped to achieve the study objectives and sustain the research originality. Questionnaire was adopted as the appropriate research instrument to collect primary data. The instrument had the structure of close-ended questions. This helped the researchers to stay focused to obtain well coordinated responses that can be assessed. The research instrument was subjected to validity and reliability testing. Validity is the extent to which the research instrument is able to measure what is intended to be measured by the researchers in a study (Nayak & Singh, 2021). Categorically, the face validity of the instrument was ascertained by experts of academia, and practitioners with adequate knowledge of the subject in discourse. Going forward, the content validity was derived from research instruments used by other researchers, modification where necessary was minimal (Creswell, 2009). The construct validity of the instrument was ascertained through the convergent

and discriminant validity. In this study, according to the rule of thumb, a convergent validity was accepted when the average loading was equal to or greater than 0.7 (Nayak & Singh, 2021). On the other hand, the discriminant validity was accepted when the variance extracted was greater than the correlation square (Chivanga & Monyai, 2016).

Reliability simple means the extent to which a measuring instrument is accurate and consistent. It explains if the instrument will yield the same or approximately the same result if tested several times (Creswell, 2009). In the aspect of reliability, composite reliability was determined by the average variance extracted. We adopted the threshold of 0.5 for our average variance (AVE) and 0.6 for composite reliability as agreed in the text by Nayak and Singh (2021). Also, Composite reliability is achieved when values are between 0.6 and above (Johnson & Rasulova, 2017). From findings, when the average variance extracted for each construct is greater than 0.5 and a composite reliability for each of the constructs is greater than 0.6, then the constructs are considered reliable (Creswell, 2009). Essentially, previous studies mentioned in the empirical review, validated the constructs and confirmed the reliability for the variables studied. Frequency distribution, descriptive statistics, simple linear regression analysis were used to analyse primary data in order to answer the research questions and test the stated hypotheses.

Results

A total of seventy staff comprising NMU, SDU, and DOU volunteered to partake in the study. Out of 70 copies administered, sixty-six (66) questionnaire representing about (94%) were returned, and four (4) questionnaire representing (6%) were not returned. Table 1.1 below shows the details of the response rate.

Table 1.1: Analysis of Response Rate

Number of Questionnaires Distributed	Respondent	Percentage (%)
Copies of questionnaire retrieved	66	94.28
No of questionnaire not retrieved	4	5.714
Total Distribution	70	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 1.2: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Main Factor	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	36	55
Female	30	46
Total	66	100
Age		
20-29years	22	34
30-39years	30	46
40-49years	12	19
50years and above	2	3
Total	66	100
Marital Status		
Single	42	64
Married	11	17
Others	13	19
Total	66	100
Educational qualification		
HND/BSc	36	55
MSc/MBA	14	21
PhD	10	15
Others	6	9
Total	66	100
Universities		
SDU	20	31
NMU	37	56
DOU	9	14
Total	66	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 1.2 shows personal profile of respondents. The Table 1.2 by Gender revealed 36 (55%) were male while 30 (46%) were female; an indication that majority of the respondents were male. By Age it shows that 22 (34%) respondents were between the ages of 20-29 years, 30 (46%) respondents were between 30-39 years, 12 (19%) were between 40-49 years, while 2 (3%) were 50 years and above. Furthermore, results on marital status showed that 42 (64%) of the respondents were single while 11 (17%) were married and 13 (19%) preferred not to say, which indicates that majority of the respondents are single or engaged. By academic qualification the study revealed, 36 (55%) were graduate while 14 (21%) and 10 (5%) had MSc or MBA and PhD respectively. This indicates that majority of the respondents are graduates. Lastly, the result on the universities sampled indicates that 20 (31%) of the respondents are SDU, 37 (56%) of the respondents are of NMU while 9 (14%) of the respondents are of DOU. This result indicates that most of the respondents are of NMU.

The analyzed data follows the research objectives and hypotheses formulated as follows:

Statement of Objective**Objective 1: Investigate the relationship between task-based participation and digital citizenship behaviour.**

The first specific objective is to examine the relationship between task-based participation and digital citizenship behaviour of NMU, SDU and DOU. The descriptive results are shown in Tables

1.3 a scale of 1 to 5 was provided where: 1=Strongly Agree (SA), 2=Agree (A), 3=Undecided (U), 4=Disagree (D) and 5=Strongly Disagree (SD).

Table 1.3: Descriptive Analysis of Task-based participation

Statements	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.
Does your department value creative new idea and solutions in solving problems	18 (28%)	15 (23%)	20 (30%)	4 (6%)	9 (14%)	3.44	1.326
Do you have research and development that ensure innovation over competitors	18 (27%)	15 (23%)	20 (30%)	4 (6%)	9 (14%)	3.44	1.326
Does your school have any product/services due to innovation	18 (27%)	15 (23%)	20 (30%)	4 (6%)	9 (14%)	3.44	1.326
Average						8.03	3.094

Table 1.3 shows that level of task-based participation between the selected public universities is high. The results in Table 1.3 yielded an average mean of the responses of 10.05 which means that majority of the respondents were agreeing to the statements in the task-based participation scale.

Table 1.4: Descriptive Analysis of Digital citizenship behaviour

Statements	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.
The Attainment of staff/student satisfaction as organizational goals has significantly increased.	15 (23%)	18 (27%)	20 (30%)	4 (6%)	9 (14%)	3.39	1.288
The Attainment of ICT support systems has significantly increased.	13 (20%)	20 (30%)	20 (30%)	4 (6%)	9 (14%)	3.36	1.260
The attainment of positive organisational culture has significantly increased.	9 (14%)	24 (36%)	20 (30%)	4 (6%)	9 (14%)	3.30	1.202
Average						10.05	3.75

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The results in Table 1.4 show an average mean of the responses of 10.05. Meaning that majority agreed to the statements in the digital citizenship behaviour scale.

Statement of hypothesis (H0₁): there is no significant relationship between task-based participation and digital citizenship behaviour of selected public universities in Delta State

Table 1.5: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis for effect of task-based participation and digital citizenship behaviour

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.984 ^a	.969	.968	.667

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
(Constant)	.541	.230		2.355	.022	.082	1.000
Task-based participation	.923	.021	.984	44.365	.000	.881	.964

a. Dependent Variable: Digital citizenship behaviour

b. F – value: 1968.275 sig: 0.0000

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Restatement of hypothesis (H0₁): there is a significant relationship between task-based participation and digital citizenship behaviour of selected public universities in Delta State

The results on Table 1.5 disclosed task-based participation exert a significant positive impact on digital citizenship behaviour of the selected public universities ($\beta = .923$, $t = 44.365$, $p < 0.05$). The magnitude of 0.923 implies that a unit increase in task-based participation will lead to 0.923 unit increase in digital citizenship behaviour of the selected public universities. This result aligns with the study of Barbu et al. (2020), also Omodu (2025) who found that task-based participation positively influences employee performance. In addition, the R^2 measures the degree at which task-based participation explained digital citizenship behaviour is 96.9%. Also, F-statistics ($F = 1968.275$) demonstrates overall significance far from zero. It is an indication that all estimated regression coefficients are highly significant.

Statement of Objective 2

Objective 2: To examine the relationship between representative participation and digital citizenship behaviour of selected public universities in Delta State.

The responses gathered from the statement on the relationship between representative participation and digital citizenship behaviour are as follows:

Table 1.6: Descriptive Analysis of Representative participation

Statements	S	A	U	D	S D	Mean	Std. Dev.
Does your school encourage their employee voice to take initiatives using new ideas and technique	18 (28%)	22 (33%)	13 (20%)	4 (6%)	9 (14%)	3.55	1.326
Does adopting strategic plans affect the outcome of management decisions in my organization	18 (27%)	15 (23%)	7 (11%)	17 (26%)	9 (14%)	3.24	1.447
Does your school have any product/services due to advocacy innovation	18 (27%)	24 (36%)	11 (17%)	4 (6%)	9 (14%)	3.58	1.325
Average						7.98	3.215

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

According to the data in Table 1.6, the average mean of the responses is 7.98. This means that majority of the respondents were agreeing to the statements in the representative participation scale.

Statement of hypothesis (H0₂): there is no significant relationship between representative participation and digital citizenship behaviour of public universities in Delta State

Table 1.7 Summary of Simple Regression Analysis for the relationship between representative participation and digital citizenship behaviour

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.966 ^a	.934	.931	.981

a. Predictors: (Constant), Representative participation

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		
	B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.791	.365		2.167	.034	.061	1.520
	Rep participation	2.68	1.856	0.981	5.518	0.534	-1.029	6.39

a. Dependent Variable: Digital citizenship behaviour

b. F- value 292.329 sig 0.000

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Restatement of hypothesis (H0₂): there is a significant relationship between representative participation and digital citizenship behaviour of public universities in Delta State

The results on table 1.7 disclosed that representative participation has a significant positive impact on digital citizenship behaviour of the selected universities ($\beta = 2.68, t= 5.518, p<0.05$). The magnitude of 2.68 implies that a unit increase in NMU, SDU and DOU relationship with their stakeholders will lead to 2.68 increase in digital citizenship behaviour of the selected public universities. This result corroborates the findings of Bano (2025) and Alonta et al. (2025) that work relations as a strong influence on digital citizenship behaviour. In addition, the R^2 degree at which representative participation explained digital citizenship behaviour is 93.4%. Also, F-statistics ($F=292.329$) measures overall significance. The model indicates that all the estimated regression coefficients are statistically significant.

Objective 3: Examine the relationship between pseudo-participation and digital citizenship behaviour of selected public universities

The responses gathered from the statement on the relationship between pseudo-participation and digital citizenship behaviour are as follows:

Table 1.8: Descriptive Analysis of pseudo-participation

Statements	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.
Does your university causally incorporate solutions to staff and student need in your academic services	18 (27%)	4 (6%)	31 (47%)	4 (6%)	9 (14%)	3.27	1.307
Does your school causally establish a new outreach for target students and employees	18 (27%)	15 (23%)	20 (30%)	4 (6%)	9 (14%)	3.44	1.326
Does your school introduce causally new academic services or operating techniques different from their competitors	18 (27%)	7 (11%)	28 (43%)	4 (6%)	9 (14%)	3.32	1.315
Average						10.03	3.948

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

The responses in Table 1.8 yielded an average mean of 10.03. An indication that majority of the respondents agreed to the statements in the pseudo-participation scale.

Statement of hypothesis (H0₃): there is no significant relationship between pseudo-participation and digital citizenship behaviour of public universities in Delta State

Table 1.9: Summary of Simple Regression Analysis for the relationship between pseudo-participation and digital citizenship behaviour

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.985 ^a	.971	.969		.653

a. Predictors: (Constant), Pseudo-participation

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		
	B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.550	.225		2.447	.017	.101	1.000
	Pseudo-participation	.838	1.079	.978	11.774	1.219	0.585	4.896

a. Dependent Variable: Digital citizenship behaviour.

b. Predictors: constant pseudo participation; F-value 686.778; sig 0.000

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Restatement of hypothesis (H0₃): there is a significant relationship between pseudo-participation and digital citizenship behaviour of public universities in Delta State

The results on Table 1.9 disclosed that pseudo-participation has a significant positive impact on digital citizenship behaviour ($\beta = .838, t= 11.774, p<0.05$). The magnitude of 0.838 implies that a unit increase in selected universities' will lead to 0.838 increase in their digital citizenship behaviour. This result validates the findings of Bano (2025); Alonta et al. (2025); and Omodu (2025) whose studies found that pseudo-participation has a positive influence on digital citizenship. In addition, the R^2 which measures the degree at which pseudo-participation explained digital citizenship behaviour is 97.1%. Also, F-statistics ($F=686.778$) measures overall significance. It is an indication that all estimated regression coefficients are highly significant.

Interpretation and Discussion of Findings

Objective 1: Examine the relationship between task-based participation and digital citizenship behaviour of selected public universities in Delta State.

The results on Table 1.5 disclosed task-based participation exerts a significant positive impact on digital citizenship behaviour of the selected public universities ($\beta = .923, t= 44.365, p<0.05$). The magnitude of 0.923 implies that a unit increase in task-based participation will lead to 0.923 unit

increase in digital citizenship behaviour of NMU, SDU and DOU. This result is in line with the findings of Omodu (2025), and Maikudi et al. (2025) who found that task-based participation positively influences digital citizenship. In addition, the R^2 which measures the degree at which task-based participation explained digital citizenship behaviour is 96.9%. The F-statistics ($F=1968.275$) measures overall significance. The figures show that all estimated regression coefficients are statistically significant.

Objective 2: Examine the relationship between representative participation and digital citizenship behaviour of selected universities in Delta State.

The results on Table 1.7 disclosed that representative participation has a significant positive impact on the digital citizenship behaviour of the selected universities ($\beta = 2.68$, $t= 5.518$, $p<0.05$). The magnitude of 2.68 implies that a unit increase in the firm's representative participation will lead to 2.68 increase in digital citizenship behaviour of the selected universities. This result corroborates the findings of Bano (2025) and Abome et al. (2025) who found that representative participation has a positive impact on digital citizenship. In addition, the R^2 which measures the degree at which representative participation explained firm performance is 6.00. The F-statistics ($F=292.329$) measures overall significance. Showing that all the estimated regression coefficients are statistically significant.

Objective 3: Examine the relationship between pseudo-participation and digital citizenship behaviour of selected universities in Delta State

The results on Table 1.9 disclosed that pseudo-participation has a significant positive effect on the digital citizenship behaviour of NMU, SDU and DOU ($\beta = .838$, $t= 11.774$, $p<0.05$). The magnitude of 0.838 implies that a unit increase in the pseudo-participation will lead to 0.838 increase in digital citizenship behaviour of the universities. This result validates the findings of Shoaib et al. (2025); Alonta et al. (2025); and Maikudi et al. (2025) whose studies found that pseudo-participation has a positive impact on digital citizenship. In addition, the R^2 which measures the degree at which pseudo-participation explained digital citizenship behaviour is 97.1%. Also, F-statistics ($F=686.778$) which measures overall significance of the model indicates that all the estimated regression coefficients are highly statistically significantly different from zero.

Conclusions

Empirical reports from data analyzed and literature reviewed lend the following conclusions and recommendations. Employee participation directly relates with digital citizenship behaviour. The study shows that cultivating joint critical thinking through employee participation in digital literacy, is not just a set of rules to follow but a philosophical approach that would bridge the gap between old and new paradigms in the education sector.

The literature reviewed in conjunction with extant theories applied such as the Adam's Equity theory, also shows that the current Public University system is more concerned with getting work done through people manually, just to mentor students to become graduands. There is fear in AI and no commonality in interest digitally. However, the competition is high in the education space with private schools and schools abroad, attracting the best digital brains as students and employees. It is revealed that academic employers with no inclusive and flexible mentality often lose valuable employees and students to rivals who seemed to have better digital citizenship behaviour.

Recommendations of the Study

From the prior findings and conclusions reached relative to the variables studied, the following are the recommendations;

- i. AI task-based participation should be encouraged to boost digital knowledge, technological tools procurement, and sustainable work environment.
- ii. For the fact that economic situations are fluid, managers and principal officers are advised to continually develop contingent approaches in achieving personal and organisational goals and objectives.
- iii. The Successful implementation of AI technologies is critical to the theoretical underpinnings been justified. Therefore managers and principal officers should explore the Adam Equity Theory, to improve on their sense of equity and teamwork for the timely achievement of organisational objectives.
- iv. Finally, to ensure best outcomes in digital literacy, AI task-based participation and execution should be closely monitored.
- v. There are previous studies on employee participation in Nigeria, and digital citizenship in other countries respectively. However, empirical studies on the combined subject matter 'employee participation in AI and digital citizenship behaviour of Public Universities Nigeria' is lacking. There are studies on the topic 'digital citizenship' relating to students but none on Nigerian University academic staff in the Niger Delta. Hence, findings contribute to existing body of knowledge.

References

- Abome, I. S., Nwadukwe, H., & Ekoriko, E. A. (2025). Influence Of Labor Relations Strategies On Employee Effectiveness In Selected Universities In South-South Nigeria. *Humanities* 6 (1), 22-29.
- Adesina, I. A & Egbuta, O. U. (2025). Strategic Reward And Recognition Systems: Driving Employee Engagement And Retention In Talent Management Practices.
- Akinbo, T. M. (2025). Revolutionizing Pedagogy: Fostering Technology Adoption And Engagement Among Teaching Staff In Ibadan'S Private. *Journal For The Psychological Studies of Social Issues*, 28(1).
- Alabi, A. O., & Mutula, S. (2025). Information And Communication Technologies: Use And Factors For Success Amongst Academics In Private And Public Universities In Nigeria. *South African Journal Of Information Management*, 22(1), 1-8.
- Bano, D. M. (2025). Digital Workplace And Employee Engagement: A Sociological Study On The Impact Of Information System On Management Strategies. *Journal Of East-West Thought* (Jet) Issn (O): 2168-2259 Ugc Care I 15 (1), 306-317
- Barbu, A., Ichimov, M.A.M., Costea-Marcu, I.C., & Militaru, G. (2025). Exploring Employee Perspectives On Workplace Technology: Usage, Roles, And Implications For Satisfaction And Performance. *Behavioural Sciences*. 15(1), 45. <https://doi.org/10.3390/Bs15010045>
- Creswell, J.W. (2009). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed methods Approaches*. Sage Publishers.
- Dupuis, M & Massicotte, A. (2025). Worker Participation Under Digitalisation: Structure, Power And Varieties Of Union Influence In Two Manufacturing Sectors. *Economic And Industrial Democracy*, 0143831X241311406.
- Imasuen, O.F., & Chinwe, N. O. (2025). Developing A Competitive Advantage Through Human Capital: The Roles Of Hrm In Strategic Business Management In Nigeria. *Ijbems*, 2941-9638.
- Jackson, N., & Carter, P. (1993). 'Paradigm Wars': a response to Hugh Willmott.

- Johnson, S & Rasulova, S.(2017). Qualitative and the evaluation of development impact incorporating authenticity into the assessment of rigour. *Journal of Development Effectiveness*, 9(2) 263-267.
- Maikudi, M., Barkindo, A., & Ahmadu, I. (2025). The Mediating Effect Of Job Satisfaction On The Relationship Between Employees Participation And Employee Commitment In Public Universities In Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Journal Of Management Science And Entrepreneurship*.
- Mishra, A., Biswal, S., & Mallick, C. (2025). Impact Of Human Resource Crisis Management On University Faculty Performance In e-Technology During Covid-19. *International Journal Of Internet Manufacturing And Services*, 11(1), 58-72.
- Nayak, J,K & Singh,P.(2021). *Fundamentals of Research Methodology: problems and prospects*. New Delhi. SSDN Publishers and Distributors.
- Omodu, N.S. (2025). Utilisation of Artificial Intelligence In Staff Mentoring And Teaching Effectiveness In Public Universities In Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal Of Educational Management, Rivers State University*. 1 (1), 142-160, 2025.
- Shoaib, M., Qadeer, N., & Zamecnik, R. (2025). Towards a Greener Tomorrow: Investigating The Nexus of Ghrm, Technology Innovation, And Employee Green Behaviour in Driving Sustainable Performance. *Cogent Business & Management* 12 (1), 2442095.